

A Study on the Entrepreneurship Skills and Opportunities for Librarian

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Introduction :

Entrepreneurship as a concept was also described by Hisrich as a process of creating something new with value, devoting necessary time and effort, assuring of accompany of financial psychic, and social risks, and receiving the rewards of monetary and personal satisfaction and independence. Librarianship as a profession provides a variety of employment opportunities. Most of the library science professionals (Library and information science) choose employment for their career prospects. The employment avenues in the library field are limited and the number of graduating library and information science professionals are increasing year by year and hence the unemployment increasing rapidly in the library and information science field. Due to unemployment in library information and science field, few library information and science professionals are forced to migrate to other jobs.

To retain the library information and science professionals in the same field and to serve Library field, there is an urgent need to explore the alternative to the library information and science jobs. The best and alternate solution would be

entrepreneurship, where library and information science professionals may start a venture in the library and information science field and become budding entrepreneurs which shall be coined as Librapreneurs.

Entrepreneurship evolved as a Career :

Entrepreneurship is becoming an increasingly popular alternative career choice in the current economic slowdown. It can play a major role in alleviating poverty, unemployment and underemployment. The library and information science graduates who have burning desire to make profession as a hobby and aim to accomplish, build an enterprise, wish to be independent, enjoy freedom and challenges in this field may opt entrepreneurship as a career and become a Librapreneur. To become a successful Librapreneur, one has to work hard, has a strong vision and mission, determination, need to dedicate long hours and endless energy.

Entrepreneurship Education in Library and Information Science :

Entrepreneurship education was introduced to library and information science with a view to stem the scenario whereby many librarians remained unemployed after graduation. The cardinal objective of entrepreneurship education is to equip students with skills that would enable them to be self-employed and create employment for graduates of Library and Information science. It is disheartening to observe that despite the introduction of entrepreneurship education in library and information science many graduates remain unemployed and these clearing points to the fact that the objective of the course has been defeated. While in most universities have initiated the programmed, little research is available to assess its impact and also to confirm if a relationship exists between students taking course in entrepreneur and their intention of becoming entrepreneurs. Library and information science as a discipline is designed to produce information professional that will competently serve different stakeholders for development. The graduates of library and information science ought to be empowered through practical entrepreneurial skills. The graduates-to-bearer expected to draw from the various entrepreneurial well of knowledge and be repositioned for job creation.

Some of the skills required for successful Entrepreneurship:

- Information technology skills.

- Information literacy skills.
- Managerial skills.
- Personal entrepreneurial skills.
- Technical skills.

Entrepreneurial Competencies :

A LIS professional who interested in starting a venture in library and information science field should possess the following entrepreneurial competencies which are a combination of knowledge, skills and appropriate motives or traits that an individual should possess to perform a given task:

- Commitment to Work Contract
- Efficiency Orientation
- Systematic Planning
- Problem Solving
- Self-Confidence
- Assertiveness
- Persuasion

These soft skills shall underlie characteristics of a person which result in effective and superior performance of a job. Competencies may be hard and soft, but they can see in successful entrepreneurs. These competencies can be developed through proper training interventions.

Entrepreneurial Opportunities :

The following are the few entrepreneurial opportunities for Librapreneurs. Interested LIS professionals may explore the possibilities to start a new venture and become successful and fulfill their entrepreneurial dreams.

- Book Distribution Agency
- Periodical Subscription Agency
- Newspaper Dealership

- Book Shop
- Stationary Shop
- Binding Workshop
- Lending Library
- Reading Room

Conclusion :

The job opportunities in the library and information science field are becoming increasingly difficult to prepare the library science professionals to explore the entrepreneurial opportunities in this field. The various entrepreneurial opportunities for the budding library science professionals associated with Library and Information Science field. Also to introduce the entrepreneurship as an elective subject in the curricula so that the library science professionals may chose new avenues in the field and may contribute to the economy growth of the country. To achieve this, the aforementioned obstacles to the success of entrepreneurship should be looked into regularly.

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